

MIXTRACT: AN ENVIRONMENT FOR DESIGNING MUSICAL PHRASE EXPRESSION

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ABSTRACT

Music performance is processing to embody musical ideas in concrete sound, giving expression to tempo and dynamics and articulation to each note. Human competence in music performance rendering is enhanced and fostered by supplementing a lack of performance skill and musical knowledge using computers. This paper introduces a performance design environment called Mixtract, which assists users in designing “phrasing,” and a performance design guideline called the Hoshina-Mixtract method executable on Mixtract. Mixtract provides its users with a function for assisting in the analysis of phrase structure and a function to show the degree of importance of each note in a phrase group. We verified that the proposed system and method help seven children to externalize their musical thought and help them transform their subjective musical thoughts into objective ones.

1. INTRODUCTION

Making and performing music is regarded as very effective ways to foster musical competence. However, in many cases, lack of control or skill with musical instruments can limit the ability to test a personal free musical thought.

If people can use a computer system to test their musical thought, listen to their attempts in the form of sound feedback, and receive assistance with their limited skill, their musical competence will likely increase.

Some music composition systems that transform graphic materials into sound are available for this goal. UPIC [2], designed by Iannis Xenakis in 1977, is the most famous and historically important system. The software version of UPIC, called Iannix, is currently available in a Max/MSP environment. For a commercial software package, Kid Pix, released in 1989 [7] for Macintosh, is regarded as the first edutainment application for children to enjoy creating sound sequences by drawing graphic icons. One study used interactive composing environments to return a musical passage in response to a play-

er’s input, which has been used for music education purposes [3].

This study deals with competence in performance rendering rather than musical composition. Performance rendering is a process of creating a musical idea as a vivid movement of loudness, tempo and articulation of note sequences. Musical performance interfaces based on beat tapping or conducting interfaces are available for this purpose [9][11][12]. In contrast with these real time applications, our study aims at letting users more carefully consider performance rendering based on phrasing. Phrasing is musical expression related to vocalization and respiration. This musically important expression is easy for people to grasp. However, it is not easy to understand how to control phrasing. Moreover, structuring phrasing is difficult without guidelines. The authors have been developing a performance design system called Mixtract to cope with this difficulty and have formalized a music interpretation theory to be used on Mixtract [6]. That is, we provided an environment to test musical thought regarding phrasing with sound feedback for users who lack performance skills.

The construction of this paper is as follows. In the next section, phrasing and an overview of Mixtract are introduced. The Mixtract overview is followed by explanations of each function for assisting in phrasing design. Then, practical phrasing design methods using Mixtract and the preliminary evaluation executed for elementary and junior high school students are described.

2. OVERVIEW OF MIXTRACT

2.1 Phrasing and Mixtract

A common property of all music is that all adjacent notes are musically connected, and the sequence of successive notes forms a musically meaningful group, which is referred to as a “phrase.” Phrases are also combined with each other to construct the phrase structure.

The phrase structure of a musical piece is not always unique. There are many possible candidate phrase structures. Musicians and conductors select one of the possible phrase structures and embody it in sound, as the structure is conveyed to the audience, as shown in Figure 1. There are various ways to express a phrase structure. The com-

Figure 1. An image curve of phrasing (from [8]). The horizontal axis shows the timeline, and the vertical axis shows dynamics and tempo. Phrases consist of a hierarchical structure, and there are rainbow-shape curves of dynamics, tempo and articulation in each phrase.

combined expression of tempo, dynamics and the articulation of each note of the piece are heard as the individuality of the performer.

In the construction of a design assistant system, it is important to ensure considerable flexibility for users. However, too much flexibility can confuse users. The following two priorities must be considered in designing a musical design assistant system: (1) The system can function as an environment in which to test a user's musical ideas with real sound, and (2) the system provides automatic functions to complement the user's input while maintaining the user's intention. Mixtract is a musical expression design-supporting environment based on the above ideas.

Figure 2 shows an overview of Mixtract. Users of Mixtract first put a score into the system by hand on the piano roll editor view or by importing a MusicXML file. Next, they specify groups of notes as phrases and give them expression (dynamics, tempo and articulation) curves.

Musical expressions given by expression curves are consistently consolidated into the whole expression. The onset time, the offset time and the dynamics of each note may be individually edited, if desired. Every time the user edits one of the expression curves, the piano roll that shows the performance preview is updated. Mixtract allows users to listen to the performance at any editing stage. This feedback is effectively used in performance design.

Our policy in designing Mixtract is that users are responsible for performance design tasks, including determination of phrase structure and editing the expression curves. Automatic processing technology is employed to fill in where users lack skill or have no special requirements. The following functions based on cognitive music theories are provided for this goal.

2.1.1 Hierarchical Phrase Structure Analysis

In order to free users from the tedious work of giving a hierarchical phrase structure to the system, Mixtract supports an automatic analysis of hierarchical phrase structure that preserves user-provided phrases. This function is based on *A Generative Theory of Tonal Music (GTTM)* [10].

GTTM itself does not offer a solution to ambiguous phrase structure. It can, however, effectively make up the remainder of the structure that the user does not directly specify. The detailed design of the interactive features of GTTM will be described in a later section.

Figure 2. Overview of Mixtract

2.1.2 Phrasing Design Based on Apex Note

There are two well-known principles of phrase expression: (a) giving an accent of velocity to the beginning note of a group and (b) rainbow-shape expression [1]. Rainbow-shape expression increases dynamics and tempi from the beginning note and then decreases them to the last note of that group.

These principles of phrase expression are simple. However, it is confusing to decide whether to employ (a) or (b) and to find the apex note of phrase in (b). To solve this difficulty, we formalized a musical interpretation theory [8] proposed by Hoshina, one of the best supervisors of directing brass bands in Japan. He showed the existence of the apex notes of phrases and an outline of how to find the apex notes through score analysis. Mixtract provides users with an apex probability viewer, as shown using several shades of red in Figure 3. A policy of editing an expression curve to make the apex fall at the apex note contributes to reducing the amount of trial and error in finding good expression curves.

3. EDITING PERFORMANCE CURVES AND SYNTHESIS OF EXPRESSION

Mixtract provides a performance design GUI using expression curves for each phrase and an editor for the start timing, duration and dynamics of each note. In this section, we illustrate the performance design interface using expression curves and describe its representation algorithm.

3.1 Editing Expression curves

When a phrase structure is fixed, the system prepares default shapes for the expression curves: tempo curve, dynamics curve, and articulation curve. When users of the system click a phrase, the expression curve editor, as shown in Figure 3, appears. The users participate the performance design by editing the expression curves.

3.2 Tempo Curve and Calculation of Note-on and Note-off Timing

A tempo curve value is given using exponent representation; 0: no change, 1: tempo-up to double, -1: tempo-down to half. The total tempo expression of hierarchical phrases is expressed by the following equation:

$$Tempo(t) = \sum_{k=1}^n \omega_k \times GroupTempo_k(t) \quad (1)$$

where $GroupTempo_k(t)$ is the tempo curve of the phrase that locates the score time t , and ω_k is the weight of the curve of the phrase. Note-on and note-off timing are calculated by the integration of $Tempo(t)$. The real time between score time t_0 and t_1 , denoted as $Time(t_0, t_1)$, is calculated using the following equation:

Figure 3. Performance curves and the editor with the apex probability viewer. The toggle buttons for dynamics (blue), tempo (green) and articulation (red) turn each expression curve on or off. The curve selected by the left radio button can be edited using a mouse. The apex probability of notes is shown using shades of red in the apex probability viewer.

$$Time(t_0, t_1) = \sum_{t=t_0}^{t=t_1} DeltaDuration \times 2^{-Tempo(t)} \quad (2)$$

where $DeltaDuration$ is the value prescribed by the average tempo (beats per minute) and resolution of the integration range. This equation makes the expression of the gradual tempo change within a beat portable to a real time scheduling application such as the conducting interface.

3.3 Dynamics curve and calculation of velocity

The overall dynamics of the note is given by the summation of the dynamics curves of the hierarchical phrases, as in the timing calculation.

$$Dyn(t) = \sum_{k=1}^n \omega_k \times GroupDyn_k(t) \quad (3)$$

The dynamics of the note at score time t is given by the following equation, as the dynamics is calculated with velocity of MIDI expression.

$$Vel(t) = StdVel + Dyn(t) \quad (4)$$

where $StdVel$ is the default standard value (64).

3.4 Articulation Curve and Calculation of Note-off Timing

Articulation refers to a performance technique, which affects the transition or continuity on single note to the following note. The current version of Mixtract deals with digital keyboard instruments. In this situation, the

Figure 4. Phrase structure. Green boxes are user-specified phrases, while blue and gray boxes are the system-analyzed hierarchical phrases based on the user's phrases. Red lines are phrase boundary candidates estimated by the system.

major control parameter for articulation is the timing of each note-off.

The score time of the i th note offset, denoted as $N_{offset}(i)$, is revised using the following equation:

$$N_{offset}(i) = N_{onset}(i) + N_{TV}(i) \times GroupArtcltn(N_{onset}(i) + N_{TV}(i)) \quad (5)$$

where $N_{onset}(i)$ and $N_{TV}(i)$ are score onset time and time value of the i th note respectively. $GroupArtcltn(t)$ is the ratio of the articulation curve of the phrases at score time t . The real time of $N_{offset}(i)$ to be issued is calculated using equation (2).

3.5 Expression of Expression Marks

For the expression marks such as crescendo and staccato, which are explicitly described in the score, Mixtract provides a replacement function in the form of expression curves. Like the expression curves of phrases, these curves can be edited.

3.6 Chords and Polyphony

The data description in the current version of Mixtract adopts procedures to place all notes in a single voice part, namely, single staff notation. It is possible to generate performance expression in melodies consisting of multiple voice parts, including the chord; however, the current system is not intended for the performance design of polyphony and tempi, each part of which may proceed differently. System implementation for polyphony is one of our future plans.

Figure 5. Outline of phrase structure analysis

4. HIERARCHICAL PHRASE STRUCTURE ANALYSIS FUNCTION

Musical phrase structure is ambiguous. Mozart's Piano Sonata K.331 (see Figure 4, upper part) is often cited by books dealing with musical theories as an example of this ambiguity. Mixtract provides a function that automatically analyzes the remainder of the phrase structure that the users do not assign. The users give the primary phrase boundary that they especially want to assign when listening to melodies. In the lower part of Figure 4, the phrases in green are those given by the user, and the phrases in other colors are phrase structure obtained automatically.

The goal of the design of the structure analysis is to reflect the user's intention and direct manipulation. Figure 5 shows the overview of the function for phrase structure analysis. If the phrase part analyzed automatically differs from what the user wants, the user can edit the phrase boundary position again, and the system will analyze the remainder again. This procedure is repeated until the user obtains the desired phrase structure.

4.1 Reflection of User's Intention

The function for automatic analysis of phrase structure is based on exGTTM [5]. ExGTTM is an extension of GTTM [10], because it may work as a computational model.

There are likely to be cases in which the users' direction contradicts the automatic analysis. Mixtract gives priority to the user's grouping direction. The lower and the upper structures of the concerned phrase are combined or divided, preserving the users' direction. Then, each default preference weight of the contradictory rules for grouping of exGTTM is revised to reflect the user's preference. The user is allowed to choose the default preference weight or the revised preference weight the next time the automatic phrase structure analysis is applied. The system also supports a function to find the same motives that the user assigned, which also helps to reduce the tediousness of the task.

Figure 6. Hoshina's interpretation and Expression of the 2nd Movement of Beethoven's Piano Sonata "Pathétique": The annotated slurs are according to the Henle Edition. The brackets above the main melody indicate Hoshina's grouping, and the stars indicate the apices of those groups. The Crescendo and diminuendo are written by the author based on his expression.

4.2 Direct Manipulation

When users of exGTTM want to change some phrase boundaries, they have to influence the system's behavior by specifying the preference weight of each rule. Instead of this indirect operation; Mixtract users are allowed to edit the phrase boundaries directly. They can assign phrases intuitively by just listening to the music, without any knowledge of the meaning of each rule for grouping. This is one of the key features that nonprofessional people can use this system.

5. PHRASE APEX ANALYSIS FUNCTION

Mixtract provides a function to guide the apex note of a phrase based on the conditions that Hoshina described for how a note may be recognized as the apex: the crest in the outline of a note sequence, notes with a long time value, more strained notes in the tension-resolution structure, and so on. He also suggested that the last note of a phrase cannot be the apex. Figure 6 shows an example of apex analysis by Hoshina.

Hoshina's theory is distinctive compared with other music theories. However, it is too subjective to be directly used as a computational model. Therefore, we formalized the theory as rules, added some additional principles, and fixed the value of the point of each rule empirically as shown in Table 1 (last page). The likelihood of each note's being the apex is calculated by adding the points of the corresponding rules for the note. The result of the calculation is converted into shades of red on the piano roll, as shown in Figure 3.

6. PERFORMANCE DESIGN METHOD USING MIXTRACT AND EVALUATION

6.1 Performance Design Method

Mixtract itself is a general environment for phrasing expression design. Inexperienced musicians, including beginners and children, may be confused as to which of a lower or higher phrase should be selected to give expression or how to edit a free-hand expression curve. To reduce such confusion, we set up a set of guidelines for phrasing called HMM (Hoshina-Mixtract Method) that can be used on Mixtract, based on Hoshina's theory.

In using HMM, first the user has to specify the primary phrase line, which is a sequence of phrases composed of a few measure lengths. Some people may think that it is not easy to judge phrase boundaries simply by looking at a visual score (piano roll). However, some of the breath points of singing melodies will be phrase boundaries. Using the playback function of Mixtract, the user can specify the phrase boundaries almost intuitively. Next, the user edits each expression curve for the dynamics, tempo and articulation of the phrases of the primary phrase line, as referring the information of each phrase apex. The user directly modifies the onset time, the offset time and the dynamics of each note, if needed. The concrete steps of HMM are as follows:

Hoshina-Mixtract Method

Step 1: Specification of the primary phrase line

1. Input initial primary phrase line
2. Modify and fix the line using playback function

Step 2: Specification of the apex of each phrase of the primary phrase line

1. System shows apex candidates with probability
2. (User fixes apex notes)

Step 3: Expression design of the primary phrase line with apex information

1. System gives default parameters of expression curves based on Hoshina's theory
2. Edit expression curves
3. (Converting Expression Marks into expression curves)

Step 4: Expression design of the higher-level phrases of the primary phrase line

1. (System gives default parameters of expression curves that as they may express the phrase as a group)
2. Adjust the position of the apex and the amplitude range of each curve, if necessary.

Step 5: (Modification of the onset time, the offset time and dynamics of each note)

The procedures in parentheses are optional. The user may go back to a previous procedure at any point, if desired.

6.2 Workshops for Phrase Expression Design with HMM

We conducted a workshop to investigate the effectiveness of Mixtract and HMM in helping around children to learn phrase design. The workshop participants were five elementary school students, ten to eleven years old, and two fourteen-year-old junior high school students belonging

Figure 7. Photograph of the workshop on phrase expression using Mixtract for seven children.

to a brass band club at their school. The workshop was led by a high school music teacher who also teaches children to play the piano and who majored in piano and completed a master's degree in music. None of the participants had ever studied music in depth, although some could play piano and some could play a brass instrument. Figure 7 shows some photographs of the workshop.

After the workshop, all of the participants commented, "It was interesting to listen to expression is changed by modifying depth of expression curves." One of the junior high school students commented, "I want to bring back the system to my home to think of phrase expression more deeply for my club activity." The following comment by the lecturer was more meaningful: "I reminded myself that I have never taught students phrasing as a general concept and a concrete methodology so far. I was made to reconsider how to teach music through this workshop. In this sense, I was a student in this workshop, too."

7. DISCUSSION AND FUTURE WORK

7.1 Mixtract as Phrase Design Environment

Mixtract is a music performance design framework that facilitates phrase expression. It includes functions that perform hierarchical phrase structure analysis and apex note analysis, and it provides an expression curve editor for each phrase.

The educational goal of Mixtract is to let its users externalize and formalize their tacit knowledge about musical performance. For this goal, it is crucial to give the users feedback on how the users' actions affect the result. The most recent version of the commercial notation software Finale [4] includes functions that render expression marks into expressive sound, and the performance rendering system SuperConductor [13] generates expressive performance based on the expression of metric structure. Commercial music sequencers are equipped with piano-roll visualization, and each has its own GUI. These systems contribute to improving efficiency in music performance production, but they are not necessarily good frameworks for letting the users consider phrasing.

The design of phrase expression in Mixtract is executed as non-real-time processing through the repetition of editing. Another computer-assisted approach to letting the user think about phrase expression is the use of performance systems that work with beat tapping or conducting interfaces such as RadioBaton [11], iFP [9] and FamilyEnsemble [12]. One of the biggest advantages of using these systems is that the player can express tempi and dynamics with simple physical movement, without worrying about pursuing the correct notes of scores. Real-time control and feedback are among the advantages of this approach. On the other hand, this function can be a disadvantage if the goal is to let the users formalize their tacit knowledge about phrase expression.

We believe that combining the use of Mixtract and a performance interface based on beat tapping could contribute greatly to increasing competence in musical performance, especially for individuals who lack performance skill and musical knowledge.

7.2 Future Work

As described in the implementation section, the current version of Mixtract is applicable to clearly multi-part music, but not to truly polyphonic music. Implementing a version for polyphonic music is a primary technical goal. The second technical goal is to provide an automatic harmonic analysis function to assist in apex probability analysis. This function will also be necessary when dealing with polyphony.

Experienced musicians already understand how to capture and express phrases, but this understanding is in the form of tacit knowledge, and even experienced musicians cannot always explain how expression is produced as a combination of dynamic, tempo and articulation of notes. We expect Mixtract and HMM to help externalize such tacit knowledge. In particular, workshops where participants can explore their expression are expected to raise not only their musical competence but also their musical culture level. Our workshop was only preliminary. We plan to continue workshops and to modify the method, and we plan to construct a curriculum for practical workshops executable by educational facilities in the near future.

8. CONCLUSION

We developed Mixtract as an environment to support musical performance design focusing on phrase expression. In this paper, we described the concept of the system design, the hierarchical phrase structure analysis and the phrase apex analysis, and we then showed an approach for phrasing called HMM that can be used on Mixtract, based on Hoshina's theory. We also described a preliminary evaluative study of Mixtract and HMM's performance for use in designing phrase expression by elementary and junior high school children.

Mixtract itself is a framework for performance design. Unlike most automatic performance rendering systems to date, Mixtract assists its user's music interpretation and helps to convey the musical interpretive intent to the system. In the preliminary study using HMM, we observed that children continued to edit curves and listen to the changes until they obtained the desired result. They were able to see the form of the expression curve together with the apex-likelihood. We are convinced that the children's subjective idea of phrase expression is shifted to an objective one through their own active editing and sound and visual feedback.

We are still at an early stage of providing a musical environment in which people are able to practice musical performance, especially focusing on phrasing, in an active environment. We hope to continue to perform experiments in the use of Mixtract by both of experienced and inexperienced musicians to foster musical competence in performance rendering and will analyze the results in future work.

9. REFERENCES

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Category	Rule	Score point of likelihood of apex			
		preceding	target	following	
	target note				
duration	first note in adjacent 2 notes	1) shorter than following note	0	1	
		2) longer than following note	1	0	
	first note of repeated notes in equivalent duration		1		
pitch	first note in adjacent 2 notes	1) lower than following note	0	1	
		2) higher than following note	1	0	
	second and later notes of repeated notes in equivalent duration		order number/note counts		
	progress note to reach the top (3rd note of 4 adjacent notes)	1) ↗ ↗ ↘	0	1	0
		2) ↘ ↗ ↘	2	1	0
		3) ↗ ↘ ↗	1	2	1
4) ↘ ↘ ↗		0	2	1	
5) ave. duration is shorter than 0.25 ms		1	0	0	
melodic tension-relaxation	appoggiatura	1) duration is longer than following note	3		
		2) duration is as same as following note	2		
		3) duration is shorter than following note	1		
		4) following note inverts	2		
		5) in conjunct motion	1		
		6) leap to following note	2		
		7) conjunct to following note	1		
		8) preceding note is a rest	1		
	suspension	if tied from preceding note	3	0	
		else	2	1	
	repeated note	if tied from preceding note	2	0	
		else	1	0	
	auxiliary note	ascending then descending	2		
		descending then ascending	1		
	passing note	ascending	2		
		descending	1		
	other ornaments (accidentals)		1		
on harmony	chord	I	0		
		I6	1		
		I46	3		
		II	6		
		IV	1		
		V	2		
		V7	3		
	VI	1			
	substitute chord	accidental	1		
		ordinary	2		
	chord change		1		
	cadence (dominant motion)	V(7) - I	4	0	
		V(7) - I6	2	3	
		V(7) - VI	2	1	
register	widen	1			
	narrow	-1			
density	double stop	1			
as phrase	beginning note	1			
	ending note	-1			
	longest note	if including bounding division	1		
		else	2		
	highest note	if longer than 0.25 sec & ave.duration in the phrase	2		
		else	1		
	most ascending & leaping note	if longer than 0.25 sec & ave.duration in the phrase	0	2	
else		2	0		
misc	articulation	accent	1		
		tenuto	1		
		non-accidental	1		
		staccato	1		
	short slur (about 1 second or shorter)	beginning note	1		
		ending note	-1		
rest	on strong beat & following note is on weak beat	0	1		
	on weak beat & following note is on strong beat	1	0		

Table 1. Rules and parameters for calculating apex likelihood